

Rhenium : Part I*. Salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ and Mixed Ligand Complexes of Re(V) with Pyridine and Cyanide

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The preparation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ by boiling the brown product obtained by the reaction between KReO_4 , KI and HCl with aqueous pyridine is described. The air-dried sample is the dihydrate, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which becomes anhydrous on drying in vacuum over P_2O_5 . The cyanide and the perchlorate salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ have been obtained by the metathesis between $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and KCN and NaClO_4 respectively. The free base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ prepared in solution by ion exchange technique is a strong one and cannot be isolated in pure state. An aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on long standing deposits $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$. In the presence of methylating agents like methyl iodide or dimethyl sulphate the yield is much improved. The substance dissolves unchanged in cold concentrated H_2SO_4 . $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$ is deposited by keeping a solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ containing a small amount of pyridine. Its coordination polymer $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_x[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]_x$ has been obtained by the metathesis between $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$.

In recent years there has been some studies on the coordination chemistry of penta-valent rhenium. A very interesting cationic oxo complex of Re(V) is dioxotetrapyridine-rhenium (V) chloride, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. Although various methods have been reported for preparing this complex, there is no complete description of a method producing a reasonable yield of pure material and different authors reported different degrees of hydration of the complex. Lebedinskii and Ivanov-Emin¹ prepared $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ by reaction between $\text{K}_2[\text{ReOCl}_5]$ and pyridine, because they observed that $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ or $\text{K}_3[\text{ReCl}_6]$ reacted with aqueous pyridine to give only hydrated ReO_2 . However, Sur and Sen² obtained $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$, together with other products by boiling an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ with pyridine in the presence of air. Johnson, Lock and Wilkinson³ have obtained the complex by boiling $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ and pyridine in ethanol and according to the authors the recrystallised product dried at 100° under 0.1 mm pressure was the dihydrate, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, while Beard, Casey and Murmann⁴ who prepared the compound from $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ and aqueous pyridine, reported the compound as a monohydrate.

All these chloro complexes from which the pyridine compound has been obtained are prepared from potassium perrhenate or perrhenic acid. It is therefore, of interest to find out a method of preparation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ starting directly from KReO_4 , thus avoiding all the intermediate stages of preparation, so that the complete preparation becomes easier

* Preliminary notes on the work were published in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 81 and 1963, **40**, 1045.

1. V. V. Lebedinskii and B. N. Ivanov Ermin, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1959, **4**, 794.
2. B. Sur and D. Sen, *Science and Culture* (Calcutta), 1960, **26**, 85.
3. N. P. Johnson, C. J. L. Lock and G. Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1054.
4. J. H. Beard, J. Casey and R. K. Murmann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 797.

and the yield is higher. In addition, it is also necessary to investigate the differences that are existent between various workers regarding the degrees of hydration of the complex. With these objects in view the problem of isolation of the pyridine complex from potassium perrhenate has been undertaken. Studies on chemical and physicochemical properties of the complex and isolation of a few salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ have also been made. It was observed that the pyridine molecules in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$ are labile and can therefore, be substituted by other groups. Studies on the formation of mixed ligand complexes of Re(V) with pyridine and cyanide were therefore made.

A study of the different methods of the preparation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ shows that the same pentavalent rhenium compound is obtained irrespective of the oxidation state of rhenium in the parent chloro complexes. It is known that⁵ by boiling a mixture of KReO_4 , KI and concentrated HCl, a brown product is obtained which contains rhenium mostly in +5 oxidation state, with a little of Re(IV). Isolation of $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ or $\text{K}_2[\text{ReOCl}_5]$ from this brown product is time-consuming. In the present work $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ has been directly obtained by boiling the brown product with aqueous pyridine.

An aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$ on long standing gave a small deposit of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$ through the simultaneous loss of two pyridine molecules. In the presence of methylating agents like dimethyl sulphate or methyl iodide which form quaternary salts with pyridine, the loss of pyridine molecules is very much facilitated and a high yield of the dipyridine compound is obtained in a very short period.

By using one mole of methyl iodide per mole of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$, the same substance, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$ is precipitated, but the reaction took a longer time (3 weeks) and the yield is poor.

The tripyridine compound $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$ is precipitated by allowing a solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$ containing a little free pyridine to stand for a few days. The tendency to lose the second pyridine molecule is hindered by the presence of excess pyridine.

It is interesting to note that $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$ may have a number of coordination polymers as shown below.

<i>No. of stoichiometric groups</i>	<i>Compound</i>
2	$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4] [\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})_2]$
3	$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_2 [\text{ReO}_2\text{py}(\text{CN})_3]$
4	$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_3 [\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$

These polymers might result by the metathesis⁻ of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ with the anions $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})_2]^-$, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$ and $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]^{3-}$ respectively which might be formed by the gradual replacement of pyridine molecules from $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ by cyanide ions in the way

5. L. C. Hurd and V. A. Reinders, *Inorg. Syn.*, **1**, 178.

Attempts for the isolation of the anions $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})_2]^-$ or $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$ as their potassium salts or precipitating them by $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ from the solutions obtained by the addition of even the calculated amounts of KCN to $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ were unsuccessful. The study of the absorption spectra of solutions containing $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and KCN in 1 : 2, 1 : 3 or 1 : 4 ratios suggested that apparently only pyridine and $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]^{3-}$ were formed in the reaction between $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ and CN^- irrespective of the amount of latter. The only polymer $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$ has been obtained in a pure state by the metathesis between $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$. It appears that this is the first example of coordination polymer of rhenium.

The direct conversion of the tetrapyridine compound into dipyridine ones by the reactions with cyanide or hydrochloric acid⁶ can be understood in terms of trans effect. The cyanide group first enters the coordination position by substituting one pyridine molecule, the loss of which is facilitated by the alkaline nature of the solution due to cyanide and is very much accelerated by the presence of methylating agents. The cyanide group in its turn weakens the Re-N bond trans to it due to its very strong trans effect. As a result, the second pyridine molecule is almost simultaneously lost and is substituted by water molecule. The two pyridine molecules in the product $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$ are thus most probably present in the trans positions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium perrhenate used was of Messrs. Johnson Matthey and Co., London (99.8% pure). Pyridine was E. Merck's Extra Pure Quality, Methyl iodide was prepared from methanol, red phosphorus and iodine. Dimethyl sulphate was of reagent quality. $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$ was prepared as described earlier⁷. Rhenium was estimated by decomposing the complexes by fusion with alkali peroxide and then precipitating rhenium heptasulphide by hydrogen sulphide from hydrochloric acid medium. The precipitate was dissolved in aqueous sodium peroxide and from sulphuric acid solution rhenium was determined by electro-deposition⁸. Chlorine was estimated by decomposing the sample by fusion with alkali peroxide or alkali carbonate-alkali nitrate mixture and precipitating chloride as silver chloride. Nitrogen, carbon and hydrogen were determined by standard micro analytical methods. Before combustion the sample was mixed with a little potassium dichromate. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made with a Gouy balance using a field strength of 8.61×10^3 gauss, the calibrant being recrystallised $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated from the data of Figgis and Lewis⁹. The diamagnetic susceptibility of pyridine was taken from Beard *et al.*'s paper⁴.

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.—An intimate mixture of 4.0 g. (0.014 mole) of potassium perrhenate and 5.8 g. (0.035 mole) of potassium iodide was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid in a porcelain basin when most of the liberated iodine volatilised away. The mixture

6. M. C. Chakravorti, Part IV of this series, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, No. 9.

7. M. C. Chakravorti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 81.

8. B. K. Sen and P. Bandyopadhyaya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 813.

9. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Modern Coordination Chemistry*, J. Lewis and R. G. Wilkins Ed., Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, N.Y., 1960, Chap. 6.

was then dried on a water bath. More acid was added which was again evaporated. This process was repeated thrice when the mixture was free from iodine. The dried mass was stirred with a mixture of 15 ml. pyridine and 40 ml. water. The whole mass was boiled under reflux for 3 hrs during which time an intense red coloured solution resulted. This was filtered warm and the red solution kept in a desiccator over sulphuric acid. After two days the large deep red crystals were separated by filtration under suction. These were powdered and then extracted with ethanol and the extract evaporated in vacuum. The yield was about 5.0 g. (60% based on the amount of potassium perrhenate taken). Beautiful large deep red crystals were obtained by slow evaporation in air of an aqueous—ethanolic solution of the substance containing traces of pyridine. For analysis the recrystallised sample was dried in air.

Anal. Found : Re, 30.4; Cl, 5.84; N, 9.42; C, 40.2; H, 4.12%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Re, 30.7; Cl, 5.86; N, 9.24; C, 39.6; H, 3.99%.

A portion of the recrystallised sample was dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 to a constant weight and analysed.

Anal. Found : Re, 32.8; Cl, 6.37; N, 9.73; C, 41.5; H, 3.60%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$: Re, 32.7; Cl, 6.23; N, 9.83; C, 42.1; H, 3.54%.

Thus, while the composition of the air-dried sample corresponded to that of the dihydrate, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the sample desiccated over P_2O_5 in vacuum was the anhydrous compound, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. The anhydrous sample was not ordinarily hygroscopic, but on very long standing in air it gradually became hydrated and was ultimately converted to the dihydrate.

The corrected magnetic susceptibility of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ at 298°K was 131×10^{-6} c.g.s. units ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.56$ B.M.). The absorption spectrum of an aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ ($1.13 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$) showed four maxima at 445 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1.15 \times 10^3$), 331 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1.60 \times 10^4$), 245 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1.35 \times 10^4$) and 230 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1.28 \times 10^4$).

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.—To a concentrated solution of 2 g. (0.0033 mole) of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ a concentrated solution of A.R. grade KCN (2.1 g.; 0.033 mole) was added with stirring. The orange precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered under suction and washed several times with small volumes of cold water. This was dried in air and then extracted with ethanol. The solution on slow evaporation deposited orange-yellow crystals. These were separated by filtration and dried in air. The yield was about 0.8 g. (40% of the theoretical). A portion of the air-dried sample was dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 to a constant weight.

Anal. of the air-dried sample : Re, 31.2; N, 11.9%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Re, 31.2; N, 11.7%.

Anal. of the desiccated sample : Re, 33.9; N, 12.4%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$: Re, 33.2; N, 12.5%.

Thus, the cyanide salt of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ like the chloride is dihydrate when dried in air, but it became anhydrous when dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 . $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$ is moderately soluble in water. It is also soluble in ethanol, but very sparingly soluble in acetone. It

loses pyridine slowly even at room temperature. The corrected magnetic susceptibility at 300°K was 51×10^{-6} c.g.s. units ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.35$ B.M.).

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$.—To a concentrated solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.0 g.; 0.0033 mole) a solution of 2.0 g (0.0165 mole) of sodium perchlorate was added with stirring when an orange precipitate was obtained. The precipitation was almost complete. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered under suction and thoroughly washed with water and then twice with small volumes of ethanol. Finally, it was dried in air. The yield was almost quantitative.

Anal. Found : Re, 29.8; Cl, 5.61; N, 8.85%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$: Re, 29.4; Cl, 5.61; N, 8.84%.

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ is very sparingly soluble in water, but soluble in acetone and ethanol. It does not lose pyridine at room temperature. The corrected magnetic susceptibility at 300°K was 107×10^{-6} c.g.s. units ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.51$ B.M.).

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$.—To an ethanolic solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ one equivalent of KOH in ethanol was added with stirring. Very soon KClO_4 separated and the solution gave very pronounced odour of pyridine. The solution was filtered free from KClO_4 . The deep orange-red solution smelling strongly of pyridine was kept overnight over H_2SO_4 when a brown precipitate appeared and the mother liquor was almost colourless. The precipitate appeared nonhomogeneous under microscope.

In a second procedure a fairly concentrated solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was slowly passed down a column of anion exchange resin (Amberlite IR 400) of OH form at a slow rate. The issuing solution was orange-red in colour, strongly alkaline and smelt strongly of pyridine. A portion of it was precipitated with diethyl ether to give a red oil which on keeping over H_2SO_4 lost appreciable amount of pyridine with the formation of an insoluble dark brown substance. It appears that in both the procedures strongly basic $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ is formed in solution, but in such alkaline solution it readily decomposes with the liberation of pyridine.

The pH of an aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ which was $7.57 \times 10^{-3}M$ with respect to rhenium was 11.14 at 28° indicating that the base is a very strong one.

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$.—To a saturated solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.5 g) excess of dimethyl sulphate (6.0 g) was added and stirred. The brown precipitate which appeared almost instantaneously, was allowed to settle for 15 min and was filtered. The residue was washed successively with water, ethanol and acetone and then dried in air. The yield was about 0.9 g (85% of the theoretical).

Anal. Found : Re, 44.8; N, 10.0; C, 29.5; H, 2.8%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$: Re, 44.3; N, 10.0; C, 31.4; H, 2.9%.

The same substance was also obtained by using methyl iodide instead of dimethyl sulphate. In this case a mixture of saturated solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.5 g) and an excess of methyl iodide (5.0 g) was kept in a sealed pyrex tube with occasional shaking. The solution first turned intense red which slowly gave a deposit of deep brown precipitate. After 5 days when the mother liquor was almost colourless, the seal was broken and the precipitate

filtered. This was washed and dried as before. The yield was about 0.7 g. Found : Re, 44.0; N, 9.9%.

Dioxycyanoaquodipyridinerhenium (V) is brown and amorphous in appearance. It does not lose pyridine on keeping. However, on drying in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 it loses one molecule of water and is converted to the anhydrous compound. Analysis of the dried sample thus obtained gave Re, 46.7; N, 10.3%. Calcd. for $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})$: Re, 46.3; N, 10.4%.

Both these compounds are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents but soluble in cold concentrated H_2SO_4 giving an intense pink coloured solution from which the original hydrated compound $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})]$ is precipitated almost quantitatively on dilution with ice-cold water.

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$.—A concentrated solution of recrystallised $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]$ CN. $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0 g) containing 0.5 ml of pyridine was kept in a stoppered flask. The solution which initially developed an intense red colour, slowly gave a violet-brown precipitate on standing for 2 days. After a week's standing, the precipitate was filtered. The mother liquor was still deep red and deposited a further precipitate on long standing. The first precipitate was washed with water, ethanol and finally with acetone and then dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 in a desiccator containing a little pyridine in a beaker. The yield was about 0.5 g.

Anal. Found : Re, 39.3; N, 11.3; C, 38.5; H, 3.1%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$: Re, 38.7; N, 11.6; C, 39.9; H, 3.1%.

Dioxycyanotripyridinerhenium (V) is a violet-brown micro crystalline substance, sparingly soluble in water and in common organic solvents. It dissolves in concentrated H_2SO_4 to give a brown solution, but the original substance cannot be reprecipitated by dilution with ice-cold water. It loses pyridine slowly even at room temperature. The analysis of an aged sample which was kept over concentrated H_2SO_4 for 3 months corresponded to the composition $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})$. The molecular conductance of a practically saturated aqueous solution ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the substance at 30° was 15.2 ohm^{-1} indicating the nonelectrolytic nature of the substance. This very small conductance may be due to the partial decomposition of the substance in such highly dilute solution.

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$.—To a concentrated solution of 1.0 g. (0.00165 mole) of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ a concentrated solution of 0.5 g (0.00114 mole) of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$ was added and the solution stirred. Beautiful golden yellow precipitate appeared almost immediately. The solution was left aside for 30 min. The precipitate was filtered and washed successively with water, ethanol and acetone and then dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The yield was about 0.8 g (75% of the theoretical).

Anal. Found : Re, 39.8; N, 11.6; C, 39.0; H, 3.0%. Calcd. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$: Re, 38.7; N, 11.6; C, 39.9; H, 3.1%.

The substance forms beautiful golden yellow crystals. This is very slightly soluble in water and insoluble in common organic solvents. Unlike the monomer $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_3(\text{CN})]$, it does not lose pyridine on standing. The molecular conductance of a very dilute solution ($1.40 \times 10^{-4} M$) which was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the substance in a

known volume of double distilled water was 422 ohm^{-1} at 30° indicating that the substance gives four ions in solution.

Isomerism in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$: The two oxygen atoms in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ could occupy either adjacent or trans-positions of an octahedron giving rise to cis-trans isomerism. On the basis of infrared spectral studies which revealed that salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ gave strong bands at 825 cm^{-1} , characteristic of a trans-dioxo group, $\text{O} = \text{Re} = \text{O}$, Johnson, Lock and Wilkinson¹⁰ showed that the two oxygen atoms in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ were trans to each other. Since only one form of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ or its dihydrate and also of other salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ could be prepared, it appears that the cis-form of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$, if it exists at all, is extremely unstable. In case, however, the salts are mixtures of the cis and the trans- forms, their resolution might be possible chromatographically.

A dilute solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ in ethanol was slowly passed down a column of Brockmann's alumina. Very little of the coloured substance was adsorbed, which again was completely eluted out by eluting twice with small volumes of ethanol. The visible and U.V. absorption spectra of the unadsorbed fraction and the two eluted fractions were identical. This shows that $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ which was not adsorbed on the chromatographic column was most probably the nonpolar trans- form. No definite conclusion could however, be drawn from these studies regarding the presence or absence of the cis-form.

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